
Fakulteta za naravoslovje
in matematiko

Research project

What have we Learned from COVID-19 Experience in Teacher Education

Project duration:

1. 9. 2021 – 28. 2. 2023

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Results:

1. Ploj Virtič, M., Dolenc, K., & Šorgo, A. (2023). What is worth retaining from the COVID-19 experience on remote online education in the prospective teacher education? *Cogent education*, 10(2, 2282308), 17.

<https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2282308>

Abstract: The COVID-19 pandemic reshaped the educational landscape, including the training of prospective teachers. This study explores prospective teachers' experiences of transitioning to online distance education (ODE) and their intentions regarding the preferred teaching scenarios they wish to use in their future in-service practice. In the sample of 281 prospective teachers, we found interesting results: (a) smartphones offer very limited opportunities for active participation in ODE; (b) connectivity is the weakest point in ODE; (c) personal digital infrastructure and study conditions influence intention to choose teaching scenarios in ODE, when in the role of teacher, while group size does not. We can safely assume that online distance education will survive in some educational pockets but due to numerous limitations, it will not become a dominant current in teacher education

2. Šorgo, A., Ploj Virtič, M., & Dolenc, K. (2023). The idea that digital remote learning can happen anytime, anywhere in forced online teacher education is a myth.

Technology, knowledge and learning, 28(4), 1461–1484.

<https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10758-023-09685-3>

Abstract: An involuntary international experiment in which the entire student population was switched to digital remote learning due to the measures to stop COVID-19 put the paradigm of "anytime, anywhere learning" to the test. Online survey responses were obtained from 281 preservice primary and subject teachers. Using Structural Equation Modelling, connections were examined by inspection of path coefficients between constructs quality of personal digital technology, satisfaction, health, well-being, motivation, and physical activity. Problems with the quality of personal digital technology had a moderate influence on all constructs except motivation. Satisfaction influenced all constructs, well-being, and health the most. When comparing responses of the bottom and top third students based on the quality of personal digital technology, it was found that students who did not have the appropriate technology and workspace were less satisfied and suffered more. This is reflected in an increased incidence of problems related to health, well-being, and physical activity, along with a decrease in motivation. At least for the technologically deprived, the paradigm of "anytime, anywhere learning" is a myth. The study highlights the need for educational institutions to provide adequate technology and workspaces for all students in order to support their well-being and motivation during remote learning.

3. Dolenc, K., Šorgo, A., & Ploj Virtič, M. (2021). Stališča in doživljanje vsiljenega izobraževanja na daljavo bodočih učiteljev v času pandemije = Views and perceived

- experiences of prospective teachers on forced remote education during the pandemic. *Mednarodna znanstvena konferenca Perspektive razvoja izobraževanja učiteljev: zbornik*, 93. https://www.conference-pef2021.si/images/PEF_Zbornik_279F.pdf
4. Ploj Virtič, M., Šorgo, A., & Dolenc, K. (2021). Activating strategies in online teaching: a case study in technical education. *PBE 2021: international conference Project-based and other activating strategies and issues of science education XIX.*, 6. https://pages.pedf.cuni.cz/pbe/files/2021/11/PBE2021_BookOfAbstracts.pdf
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 6. Šorgo, A., Dolenc, K., & Ploj Virtič, M. (2021). Didactic strategies of project-based online learning of prospective teachers in the field of biology and ecology. *PBE 2021: international conference Project-based and other activating strategies and issues of science education XIX.*, 10. https://pages.pedf.cuni.cz/pbe/files/2021/11/PBE2021_BookOfAbstracts.pdf
 7. Dolenc, K., Ploj Virtič, M., & Šorgo, A. (2022). *Fostering 21st century skills of prospective elementary, technics, and biology teachers during the COVID-19 induced university closure.* 20–28. https://pages.pedf.cuni.cz/pbe/files/2022/10/ProceedingsPBE2021_final.pdf
 8. Dolenc, K., & Fošnarič, S. (2021). Razvoj tehniške ustvarjalnosti pri študentih razrednega pouka v času pandemije virusa COVID-19 = Development of technical creativity among elementary education students during the Covid 19 pandemic. *Mednarodna znanstvena konferenca Perspektive razvoja izobraževanja učiteljev: zbornik*, 58. https://www.conference-pef2021.si/images/PEF_Zbornik_279F.pdf
 9. Dolenc, K., & Fošnarič, S. (2023). Supporting the development of technical creativity among elementary education students during the COVID-19 pandemic. V *Perspectives on teacher education and development* (str. 487–509). University of Maribor, University Press. <https://press.um.si/index.php/ump/catalog/book/770>

10. Fošnarič, S., Lozinšek, P., & Dolenc, K. (2022). Production of practical products in the subjects of environmental studies and science and technology before and after the closure of primary schools due to the COVID 19 pandemic. V *Nutrition, physical activity and health in the field of education* (str. 7–31). Dr. Kovač.
11. Ploj Virtič, M. (b. d.). What are the side effects of the Covid 19 epidemic on STEM education?: invited lecture at the International Scientific Professional Virtual Conference „Stream“ educational stream, Vilnius, Lithuania, 18th March 2022.
12. Ploj Virtič, M. (b. d.). Student activation methods in education - intensive workshop: 20 hours of lectures within Erasmus+ Staff Mobility for Teaching (STA), Charles University, Faculty of Education, Prague, 31. 10. 2022-5. 11. 2022.
13. Ploj Virtič, M. (b. d.). Teaching approaches and strategies for NST teaching: 2 hours of lectures within Erasmus+ Staff Mobility for Teaching (STA), University of Jyväskylä, Faculty of Education and Psychology, Finland, 19. 9.-21. 9. 2022.

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